

fertilizer was applied. Healthy 30-d-old Jaya seedlings were transplanted at 20×15-cm spacing. Other cultural practices were as needed.

Preplanting nematode populations per 200 cc soil did not differ significantly by year but varied within years: 122.4-134.6 in 1983 and 109.6-126.0 in 1984.

At harvest, *H. mucronata* numbers were very low in soil samples of treated nursery and treated plot (see table). Nematode populations per gram root also were low. The number of flowering tillers was higher and fresh root weight was greater. Yields increased with increasing carbofuran application. □

Control of rice root nematode by carbofuran in Orissa, India, 1983-84.^a

Treatment	Nematode population/ 200 cc soil				Population/ g root		Flowering tillers (no.)		Fresh root weight at harvest (G)		Yield/plot (kg)	
	Before transplanting		At harvest		1983	1984	1983	1984	1983	1984	1983	1984
	1983	1984	1983	1984								
T	134.6	119.4	250.2	315.2	7.20	6.20	3.48	4.80	25.30	18.44	2.2	2.7
T2	132.0	124.8	140.0	151.0	4.16	4.00	4.10	6.20	29.28	20.70	2.6	2.9
T3	134.4	109.6	69.0	90.0	2.66	3.20	4.56	6.60	34.64	26.70	3.0	3.3
T4	122.4	126.0	14.0	22.6	0.84	1.40	5.26	7.40	40.74	31.82	4.0	4.4
CD (0.05)	15.0	20.4	14.6	18.8	0.40	1.32	1.38	1.35	2.95	1.85	0.2	0.2

^aMean of 5 replications

Irrigation Water Management

Irrigation regime and rice yield

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We assessed the effect of irrigation level on rice yield (Ratna variety) during three dry seasons 1983-86. Soil was medium black, with pH 6.4, 0.87% organic C, and an infiltration rate of 1.0-1.4 cm/h. Seven treatments were replicated three times in a randomized block design.

One-month-old seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing and fertilized with 100-2241 kg NPK/ha. Irrigation treatments were scheduled immediately after transplanting. Water use efficiency was calculated on the basis of pooled means.

In all 3 yr, irrigation level significantly influenced yield (see table). Irrigation at 12 mm cumulative pan evaporation (CPE) with 60 mm depth produced significantly higher grain yield (5.5 t/ha) than with 36 mm CPE with 60 mm depth and 12 mm CPE with 120 mm

Rice yield as influenced by irrigation. Maharashtra, India, 1983-86 dry seasons.

Irrigation ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)				Water use efficiency (kg/ha • mm)	Irrigation applications (no.)	Water applied (mm)
	1983-84	1984-85	1985-86	Mean			
As required to maintain saturation	5.5	6.6	4.3	4.8	1.7	84	2815
12 mm CPE with 60 mm depth	5.1	6.4	5.0	5.5	2.3	40	2400
24 mm CPE with 60 mm depth	4.7	6.7	4.4	5.3	3.7	24	1440
36 mm CPE with 60 mm depth	3.4	6.0	4.0	4.5	4.6	16	960
12 mm CPE with 120 mm depth	4.2	5.1	3.6	4.3	0.9	40	4800
24 mm CPE with 120 mm depth	4.3	6.1	3.7	4.9	1.7	24	2880
36 mm CPE with 120 mm depth	3.8	6.9	3.9	4.9	2.5	16	1920
CD (0.05)	0.4	1.0	0.6	0.6			

^aCPE = Cumulative pan evaporation.

depth. It produced yield equal to 24 mm CPE with 60 mm depth and 24 and 36 mm CPE with 120 mm depth.

Water use efficiency was highest (4.6 kg/ha.mm) with irrigation at 36 mm CPE with 60 mm depth. The

quantity of water required was 960 mm from transplanting to maturity.

Irrigation at 12 mm CPE with 60 mm depth and 24 mm CPE with 60 mm depth resulted in equal yields, but 24 mm CPE saved 960 mm of water. □

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